

Oxidation of H_2S by Potassium Dichromate

R. C. Sharma and G. K. Chaturvedi

The oxidation of H_2S by potassium and ammonium dichromate has been studied by many workers¹⁻³. The formation of H_2SO_4 during the oxidation of H_2S by $K_2Cr_2O_7$ has been reported. In presence of alkali the formation of H_2SO_4 was retarded. In the present note, the effect of media, temperature and the concentration of the oxidising agent ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) on the amount of H_2SO_4 formed during the oxidation of H_2S has been investigated.

Procedure: To study the sulphate ion formation tendency of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ during the oxidation of H_2S by $K_2Cr_2O_7$, the procedure described by Stock and Shinozuka⁴ has been adopted.

The standard solutions of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (strength 0.05M, 0.033 M and 0.025 M) in M. HCl, M. CH_3COOH and distilled water were prepared by dissolving the calculated amount of A.R. (B.D.H.) $K_2Cr_2O_7$.

H_2S was passed through the solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ (100 ml.) till the reduction was complete. The excess of H_2S was boiled off. The clear filtrate was boiled with 5-10 ml of CH_3OH to reduce any unreacted $K_2Cr_2O_7$ in the solution. Sulphate ions in the solution were estimated as $BaSO_4$ by the usual method⁵. The data has been presented in the following table :

TABLE

Molar Conc. of Oxidising Agent	Amount of H_2SO_4 in gms estimated in terms of $BaSO_4$					
	Temperature 80°C			Temperature 60°C		
	HCl medium	CH_3COOH medium	Water medium	HCl medium	CH_3COOH medium	Water medium
0.05M	0.8687	0.7509	0.1287	0.8326	0.6849	0.1022
0.033M	0.5709	0.5011	0.0774	0.5448	0.4878	0.0653
0.025M	0.4221	0.3603	0.0605	0.4026	0.3368	0.0583

Discussion: On going through the foregoing table it is observed that the oxidation of H_2S to H_2SO_4 is enhanced by rise in temperature as well as by an increase in

1. Dunnycliff, H. B. & Soni, C. L., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 81-87.
2. Hamid, M. A., Singh, G. & Dunnycliff, H. B., *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 595-600; A, 1932, 133.
3. Dunnycliff H. B. Kotwani G. S. & Hamid M. A., *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 1217-1229; cf A. 1932, 133.
4. John T. Stock & Fujiko Shinozuka, *J. Chem. Edu.* August, 1959, Vol. 36, No 8, p. 385.
5. I. Vogel A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis, 1953, II, 479.

concentration of the oxidising agent. It is further observed that the formation of H_2SO_4 in different media is in the following order. $HCl > CH_3COOH > H_2O$ which indicates that the oxidation of H_2S is retarded at high pH.

Rational conclusion is that the oxidation of H_2S by $K_2Cr_2O_7$ depends on three important factors: (1) temperature (2) hydrogen ion concentration of the medium and (3) the concentration of oxidising agent.

Thanks are due to Dr. O. P. Bansal, Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra for his interest taken during these investigations.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
AGRA COLLEGE, AGRA.

Received November 25, 1966.